

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ALGORITHMIC MODEL USING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING TERMS IN THE FIELD OF ECONOMICS

Usmanova Umida Ilxomjon qizi

Gulistan State University, lecturer of the Department of “Russian language and literature”

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Abstract. *In this scientific article, the movement of students to creative work, search for new information in the period when the modern educational system is improving, creates the need for a thorough mastery of information and communicative technologies and knowledge of Russian languages in them. Such directions as the student's fundamental acquisition of professional and field knowledge, the fact that he begins to feel for himself how much digital economics and language knowledge are needed in order to become a globally competitive qualified specialist are highlighted.*

Keywords: *innovation, algorithmic model, competence, career, economics, competence, media literacy, communicative competence, linguistic competence, pedagogical technology, professional communication, digital economy.*

Introduction. In a period of improved internet system in our country in the conditions of modern education, there is a wide and effective use of terms in the field of Economics in the Russian language. In particular, the majority of today's young people are not just using the internet, but purposefully learning Russian from it, including communicating to them that the study of terms in the field of economics is effective for specialists in the field – the first step in language learning in this area. In this area, it is not memorization of a word that is important in language learning, but the use of the acquired word in practice.

F.A.Shirinova [1] in the research work, the student is considered as an independent, individual activity in language learning. In particular, information technology and knowledge of Russian languages are the most important aspects in improving the professional and field competence of students in non-philological directions, namely, the organization of independent activities of students in non-philological universities by means of distance education creates conditions for further formation of the self-improvement capacity of students, gives them motivation to obtain additional knowledge.

The movement of students to creative work, to search for new information creates in them the need for a thorough mastery of information and communicative technologies and knowledge of Russian languages. The student begins to feel for himself how much digital economics and language knowledge are needed in order to gain fundamental professional-field knowledge, become a globally competitive qualified specialist. This indicates that the achievement of effective results by designing the organization of independent educational activities of students through distance education in non-philological directions with an integrated orientation of the field Russian language with specialist subjects has become a pedagogical necessity today [1].

Research object and methods used

As an object of research, resources were taken in the economic literature on the teaching of all economic terms, personal approaches of the author and economic terms. The methods of

classification, description, economic-comparative, contextual, complex and functional analysis were used in the coverage of the topic of research.

The results obtained and their analysis

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Researchers [2,3] and educator — practitioners argue that computerization of education creates a separate educational environment of information exchange. In it, it will be possible to design any pedagogical cooperation, to develop the personality of an educator as a full-fledged subject of cognitive activity information and communication technologies (ICT) — a complex volumetric scientific field of knowledge, the acquisition of which requires not only a large-scale theory, but also the performance of such a number of practical activities related to the.

The main aspect of a computer as an educational tool is determined by its interactivity. B. According to Deaky [4], “Information Technology is a unique communicative-cognitive (educational-cognitive) environment in solving various didactic tasks on the study of Russian languages. Thanks to this, one of the special advantages of computer telecommunications is that it completes the electronic information environment based on an educator and close assistance to students in working with the computer as a universal means of processing information.”

Currently, it is possible to indicate the method of language teaching in distance education, through the means of information and communication technologies. Computer technology, especially using the internet, has tremendous opportunities in language learning. They manifest in the following:

1) to actively use in practice the acquired knowledge and qualifications on the relations of oral speech activity, to learn to use the language materials received not only in his speech, but also in understanding the speech of a interlocutor whom he met over the internet;

2) transfer the acquired speech knowledge to changing situations of the relationship, the formation of its adaptive skills;

3) to organize a conversation, carried out in the form of unusual communication, to create a strong, immediate motivation to learn to speak and a motivation to react close to reality;

4) elimination of interference barriers, in particular, avoidance of foreign language speaking and error, complete loss of barrier and internal and external reluctance and feeling of shame;

5) increased quality of learning to a higher level and effective outcome, as soon as the second exercise, users begin to speak a foreign language that they are learning in a speech mold given in the main training text; means of influence (including inclusion in memory) are used, and classes are taken into account as soon as the first exercise;

6) present and assimilate a large number of lexical, pronunciation and grammatical units; in one presentation, about 150-200 new words, 30-50 speech samples and several typical speech phenomena are introduced and mastered.

The methodology of intensive teaching of the Russian language in education has found its place in the primary, secondary, higher stages of the teaching process at all stages. Suggestopedic technology can complement new models of teaching to recently emerging foreign languages with new content, which include: a field teaching model, a second foreign language teaching model, a primary education model. The development of intensive technologies for the conditions of higher educational institutions opens up tremendous opportunities for the development of this direction in the following aspects:

- growth of educational indicators to the qualitative aspect in terms of quantity;
- consists in revising the proportions between independent work and audience training of teaching to all types of speech activities using suggestive technology and building new features of students and their interaction with each other;
- time-lapse distribution is the main important difference of intensive technology from the traditional method;
- intensive technology for studying programs on the Russian language cannot be applied in the whole case;
- individual styles of intensive technology can be successfully used in foreign language lessons.

It is known that the 60-70 years of the last century are considered as a period of the emergence and development of new methods of teaching a number of foreign languages, known under the general name “intensive educational technologies”. [5] All these methods, which originally arose in different countries and in different years of this period, are nevertheless a general response of the methodology to the social order of modern society.

During this period, the growing number of specialists in various fields of Science and technology, which directly carry out scientific and technical relations that occur with the world situation, the scientific and technical revolution that caused the “explosion” of information, as well as with the expansion of the circle of cultural and practical contacts, all this put their demands on the need to know a foreign language.

The condition of relations in a language considered a means of communication, obtaining and collecting information in a foreign language determines the need to know all types of speech activity: understanding and reading this foreign language, writing, the degree of knowledge of one or another type of speech activity, directly in the practice of communication in a foreign language, reading authentic and highly meaningful literature in.

Emerging as results on the social basis of scientific and technical progress, new methods of teaching, of course, include and reflect the modern levels of neuropsychology, psychology, in particular, psychology of perception, psychology of memory, consciousness and unconsciousness, psychology of Information Theory and other knowledge.

Currently, new techniques are used by other closely related and mixed disciplines-in particular, linguistics, Psycholinguistics, psychogenic experience and knowledge. Pedagogical suggestopedic (“Immersion method” – Immersion is a natural way to learn language.) direction arose due to the attempt of the Bulgarian doctor, psychotherapist Georgie Lozanov [6] in the process of reading, in particular, to use suggestopedia as a means of activating the Reserve psychic capabilities of an individual in teaching foreign languages. Suggestopia (according to Lozanov) is a means of communicative influence in the state of vivacity of a person, which creates conditions for activating the capabilities of an individual in a language experience, and not mainly directly.

G.Lozanov [7] distinguishes mainly three types in the suggestopy method. They are used in the learning process to eliminate various psychological barriers in users. They are: psychological suggestopedia, psychotherapeutic, psychological and psychogenic factors and use the logical form of communicating the material to conduct training taking into account emotional impact.

Didactic suggestopedia uses separate styles that activate education in training. Artistic suggestopedia uses different types of art (elements of music, painting, Theater) in order to emotionally influence the student in training and harmonize the training.

It is also necessary to pay attention to them in the preparation of distance lessons in education, the main provisions of the suggestopedia are as follows: :

- education should not be joyful and burdensome:
- it must be carried out both consciously and to the point of not realizing it:
- it is important to make extensive use of the usually non-participatory: non-participatory reserves of the mind in education in order to increase productivity.

Lozanov's followers were thoroughly analyzed by research scientists [8,9], and this method received the name “Lozanov” then “express method”, and later “intensive (intensive) educational technology”. Lozanov's ideas were adapted and developed into Russian language education by educators and psychologists. They established a council on the problems of intensive methods as leading specialists in intensive technologies of teaching foreign languages. This council gathered and summarized extensive results on the application of teaching intensive technologies to foreign languages and directed the work of educators on the assimilation, use of these methods. A large number of articles by proponents of intensive methodology are aimed at the correct application of intensive technology of teaching.

When teaching the terminology of texts on economics, it is necessary to clearly define the main goals and objectives of the previously intensive method. Thus, the main task of intensive technology is the acquisition of a foreign language as a means of communication and perception in a short period of time, the development of skills and skills for understanding oral speech in Russian at a simple (natural) pace on almost, unrestricted, sociopolitical and general topics. At the most elementary stage of training, the skills for understanding oral speech are improved during training, transformed into skills. Provides understanding from 50 to 100 percent of the volume of information received. In the context of practical communication, a question on issues that are not understood in terms of the content of the volume of oral speech in a foreign language or an explanation of individual parts of speech should be carried out at the expense of the listener's “speech activity in Russian” comprehension skills.

The test-work of the experiment on the study shows that in order to create a much higher level of listening skills, it is necessary for the user to occupy a vocabulary wealth equal to about 6 thousand words. This is a separate type of dictionary, the knowledge of which is carried out not only on the account of real familiar, preliminary words, but also on the account of knowledge of the rules of Word formation. This is due to the creation of a contextual awareness skill in the user, with the creation of an internal structure of the studied foreign language, which includes many unfamiliar words, and at the expense of the communication experience of each of the participants in the dialogue. Participation in communication aims to know oral speech in a foreign language, that is, to create the skills of speaking.

As a condition for the implementation of speaking skills in concepts related to the professional sphere, not so many requirements are imposed on vocabulary, the volume of language

materials. However, in order for the speaker to fully participate as a person in the process of communication, the word that the user must occupy and, in general, the volume of language materials determines the necessary minimum.

In addition to verbal and grammatical material, this minimum assumes that a number of basic extralinguistic tools of this language, such as the absolute pace of speech, the feature of breaks (their duration and location), occupy both this language and sign features. Research has shown that this language can be learned to use the tools of normative grammar and vocabulary, as well as certain tools of Stylistics:

1. Preliminary submission or explanation of the situation. In the introductory stage, the voice over the computer is expressed, emotionally, in content with the translation of each phrase in the native language. Thus, the first three phrases are introduced, which form an oral introductory course. Only unfamiliar words or phrases are then translated after the completion of this course. These phrases need to be memorized. A prerequisite for free, natural communication in explaining the new material. Explaining the situation can take up to 20 minutes, and then 5-10 minutes. When conducting an introductory course, the first three phrases are detailed and translated. Starting with the fourth, only the general situation is described and selectively translated.

2. Second submission or text explanation. This part lasts 30-40 minutes, it is conducted as follows: listening to a phrase in Russian with the help of a computer repeat the sound after the statement of the text translation once again repeat and repeat the text in Russian. Difficult phrases and individual speech models can be repeated up to 15 times. To achieve recall and lose monotony, tools such as facial expressions, gestures, pronunciation tones (expressing different emotional states, speaking different audio rhythmically, asking again, chanting individual phrases, etc.) should be used.

3. Third submission or active session. After the user listens to the pronunciation of Russian terms on the computer, he is given the instruction to translate it from a foreign language and remember it. After the oral introductory course, the user learns the written form of terms, studies and repeats the text in Russian.

By such a system (words in Russian), it is also possible to read the text simply in an emotional way. The purpose of this stage is to voluntarily remember the new material by recognition. It will take 10-15 minutes.

4. Fourth presentation or musical session. This is the last stage of entering a new text — it is done on the computer under the tones of light classical music (Vivaldi, Mozart, Gaydn, etc.). Before starting a musical session of the stage of reading text in a foreign language (without translation), such words appear on the screen: “now listen to pleasant music and listen to text in a foreign language under the sounds of music. Sit comfortably, feel free, like at a concert. You can stretch your legs and close your eyes to have more fun listening to music. So you are at a concert.” 10 minutes are allocated to the musical session. In addition to the task of resting and regaining their strength, this session contributes to the emergence of a sense of confidence in one's own strength, a sense of satisfaction with reading, since, having listened to the text a fourth time without translation, they easily perceive and understand it in a foreign language. The text is completed, it is not recommended continuing communication with the computer. Independent assignments (listening to the text in tape recorder) and all explanatory work are given before the start of the musical session. It is necessary to mention the importance of the introductory part presentation feature. The introduction of any text is effective if it consists of 4 presentations described above.

It is possible to get used to such a sequence of work over time and understand it as a guarantee of their success in mastering a foreign language. In this case, it is possible to think not about intensive education, but about accelerating education. However, L.G.Denisova (Denisova L.G. Place of intensive methods in the system of teaching foreign languages in secondary school / L.G. Denisova // Foreign languages in school. - 1995. № 4. P. 6-12.) in the article "the place of intensive educational methodology in the system of teaching foreign languages in secondary schools", the school further studied the problem of applying this method. In particular, he writes: "the authors of practical recommendations as well as methodological articles also offer many different conditions, systems in the use of "intensive interpretation within the framework of the school." All this indicates the success of applying intensive technologies in the presence of different stages of teaching the Russian language and different conditions.

It's time to systematize and highlight the most convenient methods. Let's consider intensive technology in three "sizes".

- 1) state standard for intensive technologies;
- 2) to different models of Education;
- 3) it is important to determine the suitability of education for universal requirements and goals.

Intensive technology is an educational system that arose in response to the demand of this period. In general terms, these requirements can be considered to consist in accelerating the process of teaching a foreign language with minimal effort on the part of the subject (user). Due to its adaptability to intensive technology in distance learning conditions and high educational performance, training can be applied at each stage. The objectives of each of these stages should be determined.

In independent teaching — relying on didactic principles, we understand the implementation of independent work and operations on the formation and improvement of users speech skills through Foreign Language Teaching and independent work, the development of speech skills in a certain order of methods of the educational process with a given didactic task. Independent movement and operations can be performed relying on specially designed didactic materials.

The emergence of a holistic system of training a new generation of competitive personnel on a global scale requires further improvement in the training of high-potential pedagogical personnel who have mastered Russian languages. Of great importance in this place is the assimilation of toxicological analysis and teaching methodology of terms in the field of Economics in the Russian language.

In our eyes, the toxicological analysis of terms in the field of Economics in the Russian language consists of the following structural stages:

- designing the educational process;
- Organization of the educational process on the basis of ICT tools;
- to convey the essence of the content of terms in the field of economics to students when conducting the educational process;
- assessment of the result, programming its further activities on the basis of toxicological analysis of terms and teaching technologies in the field of Economics in the Russian language. Of course, in the effective organization of this process, knowledge in the field of economics is

required not only from a specialist, but also from a student. This means that the process requires the activity, creative cooperation of both subjects.

The following are taken into account in students of communicative competence, which plays an important role in the formation of the content of the methodology for studying terms related to the field of Economics.

- factual information search (importing and seeking factual information);
- attitude training and expression (expressing and finding out attitudes);
- finding a solution to the problem (getting things done);
- socialization(socializing);
- structure communication (structuring discourse);
- re-establishing communication (communication re-pair) [10].

In this respect, the communicative competence of students studying the Russian language includes specific pedagogical conditions. Because it is necessary that the student, in addition to his native language, his homeland, customs, traditions, spiritual values, also knows the language, culture, values of another nation, makes a comparative analysis, draw conclusions, make decisions. In this place, pedagogical reflection (exchange of ideas) of a specialist, pedagogical influence is a factor in the student's deep acquisition of knowledge in science. Continuity of the process of mutual exchange of views, comparative analysis of information, reliability, objectivity are important in the lessons of the Russian language [11].

According to the opinions of pedagogical scientists, there are such directions of communicative competence, which are directly related to the factors of mutual exchange of ideas, as persuading a student, influencing his consciousness, imitating others.

The student believes in the theoretical idea expressed in the content of Science in the Russian language training, conclusions drawn on the basis of comparative analysis, worldview, consciousness, morality, behavior, meaningful speech, feedback. Through these tools, it instills its evidence and arguments in the minds of students in the future as a reflection on the peculiarities of the Russian language, the history of the country in which the language is studied, geography, demographic status, aspects of nationalism, customs, traditions, culture, art, economy, politics, etc. The self-development of undergraduate students, one of the peculiarities of the personality-oriented approach, using multimedia technologies in the creation of electronic resources and the organization of teaching the Russian language with these resources, is explained by the fact that they have their own personal experience. This leads them to be able to present the results of their activities in a convenient and understandable form through the effective use of multimedia learning materials. The use of such materials in the framework of personality-oriented education, in general, contributes to the improvement of the educational process, the formation of a holistic, intellectual and information-literate personality of a bachelor-student.

Thus, the model created by us for the introduction of multimedia tools into the process of professional training of undergraduate students in the economy of buildings and facilities allows us to reveal the content of the system for the formation of linguistic competence and meet the goals and objectives of our research. The competence problem is not only an object of research in pedagogical science, but there are also approaches to this problem in other areas.

A student preparing for training in higher education institutions can use electronic educational and methodological materials in the ICT with access to an electronic library catalog, database and electronic textbooks, while organizing his own individual educational activities. In

this, the student independently manages to acquire new knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as develop and deepen his educational and professional activities by himself.

According to the laws of linguodidactics, which developed in the 20th century as a separate discipline in education, the concepts of whom to teach, how to teach, where to teach, the psychological age of students in teaching the Russian language, as well as in what conditions to teach were analyzed. Well, in the process of developing listening comprehension speech activity, it is important to listen by students to understand the general content, listen to understand the details and receive some information — an important fact—the specificity of the specialist's perception of the surrounding reality, which leads to the creation of new cognitive maps or their transformation. Each subject sphere constitutes a conceptual sphere of a specific psychic space. Economics is one of the most extensive areas of engineering that provides our society with vital objects, and therefore this area of professional knowledge requires a multi-stage approach and presentation in the form of various cognitive maps.

The typology of existing cognitive maps includes:

- 1) general view map to display the spatial state of objects at the same time;
- 2) roadmap as a sequential image of the relationship between objects along a given route.

Their actions were performed, by reading various texts, future engineers will be able to understand the general content of materials in the Russian language, receive new information, and it was achieved that they understood the details. In particular, the effectiveness in the process of carrying out speech activity in the research work was carried out in accordance with psychological, psycholinguistic and methodological requirements.

For the first time in this study, didactic, psycholinguistic and methodological principles were clarified and established in the teaching of the Russian language using information technology to students of the direction of Economics.

It should be noted that the use of computers and internet resources creates conditions for students to receive any information they need (including regionalism) Russian language, which increases the motivation for learning and helps to expand the worldview of students. In the lesson, it is possible to carry out interactivity together from the capabilities of the computer and the internet. Thus, it is necessary that the graduate of the educational institution, along with the necessary knowledge, skills, qualifications, can use new information technologies in his activities.

Conclusion

In the process of modern education, the teaching of Russian terms to students of the direction of economics through the use of Information Technology has shown its relevance. It is he who contributes to the activation of psychological mechanisms of information acquisition (the development of their interests, the strengthening of motivations, the formation of a conscious attitude towards the acquisition of Russian languages, etc.), it was also found that the acquired knowledge, systematization of skills, their creative use will help to make it possible to carry out tasks.

Increasingly consolidating its future position as an educational tool, computer allowed creating new didactic opportunities for the prospect of builder activities, reduce the time spent on certain processes (for example, intermediate controls), developed most tasks (providing new information, distributing and issuing tasks), helped to open unlimited opportunities in collaborative activities through the use of computer communication tools.

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